

A Study of a Method of Determination of Cobalt by Complex Formation with Nioxime Reagent in Presence of Iodine

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A method is described for the determination of micro quantities of cobalt in the presence of large amount of foreign cations by extraction with organic solvents.

The complex of cobalt with nioxime in presence of iodine is completely extracted from acidic medium ($pH = 1$) with a mixture of chloroform and amyl alcohol (in ratio 3 : 1 v/v). The spectrum of this complex exhibits maximum at the region 460-470 $m\mu$. This maximum is not affected by the presence of nickel and iron. Nioxime practically has no absorption at this region.

The percent extraction of cobalt does not change in presence of nickel and iron even if they are present in ratio Co/Ni or Co/Fe = $1/2 \times 10^4$.

Small concentration of pure cobalt (0.5 $\mu g/ml$) can be determined spectrophotometrically. The presence of nickel does not interfere with the determination of cobalt even if it is present in ratio Co/Ni = $1/5 \times 10^3$ with error = 2.02%.

Molar extinction coefficient (E) of complex of cobalt with nioxime in presence of iodine at the region $\lambda = 470m\mu$ is $(0.9842 \pm 0.0405) 10^4$.

In natural combination and industrial material, cobalt often contains nickel, so it is necessary to investigate the determination of cobalt in the presence of nickel.

Many reagents have been used in the determination of cobalt¹, of which α -furyl monoxime is suggested for the determination of micro quantity of cobalt. However in the presence of nickel, cobalt can only be determined if the ratio of Co/Ni is 1/150 with an error of $\pm 4.5\%$ ^{2,3}.

Nioxime is used for the determination of micro quantities of nickel in the presence of large quantities of foreign cations. The nioxime complex of nickel is extracted with organic solvents. However complete formation of this complex is reached when $pH = 5^4$, while the complex of cobalt with nioxime in presence of iodine is completely extracted from acidic medium ($pH = 1$)⁵.

This difference in characteristics of complex of nickel with nioxime and the complex of cobalt with nioxime in presence of iodine has been utilised for the determination of cobalt in presence of large amount of nickel by method of solvent extraction.

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E X P E R I M E N T A L

In this investigation the following solutions were prepared :

1. Nioxime (1, 2 cyclohexanedione dioxime, white crystalline compound m.p. 187°) 0.5% solution of it in water.

2. Stock solution of Co^{60} : $5 \times 10^{-5} M$ (Co^{60} as perchlorate in $0.1 M \text{HClO}_4$ and $0.1 M \text{NaClO}_4$).

3. Stock solutions of $0.1 M$, each of cobalt ($\text{CoCl}_2, 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$), nickel ($\text{NiSO}_4, 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and iron ($\text{FeSO}_4, 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$) were prepared by dissolving the salts in water. 20 ml. of con. HCl was added to 1 litre of each solution. The exact concentration of cobalt solution (approx. 0.1 mg/1 ml.) was determined by α -nitroso- β -naphthol⁶. The solution of cobalt of $5 \mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ was prepared by dilution method.

4. Oxidant solution was prepared by dissolving excess of iodine in $0.2 N$ potassium iodide solution with rapid shaking for 1 hr. and filtered.

5. Buffer solutions : $p\text{H} = 1$ was prepared from 2.5 ml. of con. HCl in 100 ml. of water. $p\text{H} = 9$ was prepared from a mixture of 90 ml. of $0.05 M$ Borax soln ($\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7, 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and 10 ml. of $0.1 N$ KOH⁷.

For the determination of the percentage of extraction of the complex of cobalt with nioxime-iodine reagent, Co^{60} solution was used. The aqueous mixture of 1 ml. of Co^{60} soln + 0.5 ml. of iodine soln. + 1 ml. of nioxime soln + 7.5 ml. of buffer soln. of $p\text{H} = 1$ was shaken with 10 ml of organic solvent mixture (chloroform + amyl alcohol 3 : 1 v/v) for 1 hr. 1 ml. of the separated organic phase was measured by Scintillation counter for the concentration of Co^{60} . The concentration of Co in aqueous phase was calculated by the difference between the initial concentration and the organic phase concentration. The effect of the presence of nickel and iron on the percentage of extraction was also studied in the same way. The effect of the composition of the organic solvent mixture was also studied. The experiment was repeated at $p\text{H} = 9$.

The three solutions of cobalt, nickel and iron complexes with nioxime-iodine reagent were separately prepared as follows : The aqueous mixtures of 5 ml. of $0.1 M$ solution of each of the elements + 1 ml. of iodine solution + 1 ml. of nioxime solution + 3 ml. of buffer solution ($p\text{H} = 1$) was shaken with 10 ml. of organic solvent mixture (chloroform + amyl alcohol 3 : 1 v/v) for 1 hr. and was allowed to separate. The separated organic phase was collected and filtered. The filtered organic solution was poured into another separating funnel containing 2 g solid $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ and shaking for 30 mins. to destroy the excess of iodine. This organic solution was measured spectrophotometrically at different wave lengths for the optical density.

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For the determination of cobalt in pure salt in the presence of nickel, six separating funnels were prepared as follows : Each funnel contains the solution of cobalt (of different concentrations: 0.0 to 2.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$), 0.5 ml. of iodine, 1 ml. of nioxime solution and the remaining of buffer solution ($\text{pH} = 1$) to complete 10 ml. plus 10 ml. of organic solvent mixture (chloroform + amyl alcohol 3:1 v/v). After extraction the organic phase was collected and filtered. The excess of iodine was destroyed as before. The optical density of this organic phase was measured at $\lambda\text{-}470\text{ m}\mu$ for each solution including the blank. The exact pH of the aqueous phase after extraction was found to be 0.85.

The spectrophotometric measurements were made using Beckman *DU* spectrophotometer with the cell of 1 cm. length. The pH of all the aqueous phases were measured by *PYE* type pH -meter.

Results were treated by method of mathematical statistics⁸, where n = number of measurement

$$S^2 = \text{dispersion} = \frac{\sum(X_i - \bar{X})^2}{(n-1)}$$

where X_i = initial value,
 \bar{X} = average value ;

S = average square deflection ; $t_{\alpha, k}$ = tabular quantity distribution $\frac{t_{\alpha k} S}{\sqrt{n}}$ = exactness of determination .

$t_{\alpha, k} = f(\alpha, k)$; $K = n-1$; n = number of liberties of steps ;
 α = reliability of results.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The complete extraction of cobalt with nioxime-iodine reagent can be achieved by using the organic mixture of chloroform and amyl alcohol (3 : 1 v/v) in acidic medium ($\text{pH}=1$) (fig. 1). The percentage of the extraction does not change even if Co/Ni ratio or Co/Fe ratio is $1/2 \times 10^4$.

Fig. 1

The effect of the composition of the extraction mixture on the percentage of extraction of cobalt with nioxime-iodine reagent.

- I. Chloroform + amyl alcohol 3 : 1 v/v.
- II. Chloroform + amyl alcohol 1 : 1 v/v.
- III. Chloroform only.
- IV. Amyl alcohol only.

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The spectra of complex of nickel and iron with nioxime in presence of iodine in acidic medium do not show a maximum peak in the visible region ($\lambda = 460-470 \text{ m}\mu$), *i.e.* practically have no absorption at this region while that of cobalt has peak in this region (fig. 2).

Fig. 2

The absorption spectra of

- △ Complex of cobalt with nioxime-iodine reagent (initial organic phase was diluted 16 times)
- Complex nickel with nioxime-iodine reagent (initial organic phase was diluted 4 times)
- Complex of iron with nioxime-iodine reagent (initial organic phase was diluted 4 times)

It is found that when cobalt is determined with nioxime-iodine reagent, the intensity of absorption decreases when the concentration of cobalt increases. However when excess of iodine is destroyed completely, the intensity of absorption increases with the increase in the concentration of cobalt. (fig. 3). It was found that 2 g. of $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ was enough to destroy the excess of iodine in organic phase when shaken for 30 mins.

Fig. 3

Small concentration of cobalt (0.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) can be determined spectrophotometrically by nioxime in presence of iodine as shown in Table 1. and fig. 3. In presence of nickel, cobalt can only be determined if Co/Ni ratio is $1/5 \times 10^3$ or less with error = 2.02% (Tab. 2). Molar extinction coefficient (E) of complex of cobalt with nioxime-iodine reagent in mixture of chloroform and amyl alcohol (3 : 1 v/v) at the region $\lambda = 470 \text{ m}\mu$ is $(0.9842 \pm 0.0405) \times 10^4$.

TABLE 1

Determination of content of cobalt with nioxime-iodine reagent.

Co $\mu\text{g/ml.}$	n	\bar{X} D. 470 m μ	$S^2 \cdot 10^4$	S .10 ²	$t_{\alpha,k}$ $\alpha = 0.95$	$\frac{t_{\alpha,k}S}{n^{3/4}} \cdot 10^3$	Warrantly interval $\bar{X} \cdot 10^2$
0.5	15	0.080	1.06	1.03	2.131	0.5667	8.0 \pm 0.5667
1.0	15	0.163	2.355	1.535	2.131	0.8446	16.3 \pm 0.8446
1.5	15	0.253	10.397	3.223	2.131	1.7733	25.3 \pm 1.7733
2.0	15	0.352	4.401	2.098	2.131	1.1544	35.2 \pm 4.4010
2.5	15	0.428	0.904	0.9508	2.131	0.5232	42.8 \pm 0.5232

TABLE 2

Determination of cobalt in presence of nickel with nioxime-iodine reagent.

Co. $\mu\text{g/ml.}$	Ni mg/ml.	Co/Ni	n	\bar{X}	$S^2 \cdot 10^4$	S .10 ²	$\frac{t_{\alpha,k}S}{n^{3/4}} \cdot 10^2$	Warrantly interval $\bar{X} \cdot 10^2$
0.5	—	—	5	0.481	0.10	0.3162	0.3636	48.1 \pm 0.3636
0.5	0.5	1/10 ³	5	0.482	0.46	0.6782	0.7798	48.2 \pm 0.7798
0.5	1.0	1/2 \times 10 ³	5	0.485	0.10	0.3162	0.3636	48.5 \pm 0.3636
0.5	1.5	1/3 \times 10 ³	5	0.486	0.09	0.3000	0.0345	48.6 \pm 0.3000
0.5	2.0	1/4 \times 10 ³	5	0.485	0.15	0.3873	0.4453	48.5 \pm 0.4453
0.5	2.5	1/5 \times 10 ³	5	0.525	0.18	0.4243	0.4879	52.5 \pm 0.4879

TABLE 3

Molar extinction coefficient of complex of cobalt with nioxime-iodine reagent at $\lambda = 470 \text{ m}\mu$ in mixture of chloroform and amyl alcohol 3 : 1 v/v.

Solvent	$\frac{\bar{X}}{E_{1\%1\text{cm}\mu} \cdot 10^{-4}}$	n	$S^2 \cdot 10^{-6}$	S .10 ⁻³	$t_{\alpha,k}$ $\alpha = 0.95$	$\frac{t_{\alpha,k}S}{n^{3/4}} \cdot 10^{-3}$	$\bar{X} \cdot 10^{-4}$
Mixture of chloroform and amyl alcohol 3 : 1 v/v.	0.9842	5	0.1238	0.3519	2.571	0.4046	0.9842 \pm 0.0405

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